

Keywords:

#Data, #OpenScience, #Astronomy, #Escape,
#DarkMatter, #ResearchObjects, #EOSCinPractice

Dark Matter

The Dark Matter Test Science Project (TSP) within the European Science Cluster of Astronomy and Particle physics ESFRI research infrastructures (ESCAPE) project

The Dark Matter Science Project researchers:

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The Project Involved

ESCAPE

European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle physics ESFRI research infrastructures

This project is a collaboration between scientists in European Research Infrastructures and experiments seeking to explain the nature of dark matter (such as HL-LHC, KM3NeT, CTA, DarkSide). The goal of this Science Project is to highlight the synergies between different dark matter communities and experiments, by producing new scientific results as well as by making the necessary data and software tools fully available.

The Research Community

Many of the European Research Infrastructures within ESCAPE have experiments that are searching for Dark Matter. There is a clear complementarity between these experiments under a variety of dark matter hypotheses.

Connecting results and potential discoveries from different experiments requires the engagement of all scientific communities involved – astrophysics, particle physics and nuclear physics – as already recommended within the update of the European Strategy of Particle Physics.

The Dark Matter Science Project coordinators

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The Challenge

Besides the interpretation of results in terms of dark matter theories, synergies also exist between different communities and experiments in the tools needed to produce those results, in particular in terms of data management, data analysis and computing.

ESCAPE researchers funded by EOSC-Future have developed a Virtual Research Environment (VRE) that takes full advantage of these synergies. The VRE hosts both FAIR data and software, so that data analyses from different experiments can be executed in full.

EOSC service or tool used

The following lists the services developed by ESCAPE that are essential to this science environment and are contributed to EOSC Future:

- AAI: A fully developed AAI solution following the AARC blueprint, so scientists in the TSP's can use a single user identity for all aspects of work
- Data Lake: federated storage services with open and embargoed datasets
- Rucio – data location catalogue and policy engine. ESCAPE FTS (File Transfer Service) – for moving data around; integrated with the AAI service and the storage endpoints. Additionally: caching and streaming services to deliver data to processing and analysis. A software catalogue to publish all of the needed analysis components, and make them available for the various groups involved in the TSP work
- Virtual Research Environment: An analysis environment, with a Jupyter notebook deployment, and access to scalable compute resources, tying in all these services.

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Benefits and impact

- Entry point to the Virtual Research Environment where the workflows are implemented: <https://escape2020.pages.in2p3.fr/virtual-environment/home/>
- Delivered the services above, and implemented five different data analyses from experiments looking for dark matter (more being onboarded) on the VRE
- [Talk & proceedings](#) at the [TOOLS20](#) conference (review of state-of-the-art tools for high energy physics and cosmology)
- Engagement via Consortia (ECFA, APPEC, NUPECC, JENAS)
 - DM is a recognised challenge for the communities
 - Invited [poster](#) by DM postdoc at the [JENAS conference 2022](#)
 - [Talk](#) and upcoming paper from the [FAIR4HEP](#) workshop, to advance data & artificial intelligence (AI) models through the development of FAIR frameworks
 - Inputs to [Snowmass](#) white papers submitted to arXiv and journals [\[1\]\[2\]\[3\]\[4\]](#) (Snowmass: input to prioritisation of particle physics, deciding US's science priorities). Figures made with code that is / is being onboarded to EOSC
- Two plenary talks at the biggest international conference for computing in high energy physics (CHEP), one on the DM Science Project and another one on the VRE [\[1\]\[2\]](#)
- A full list of publications can be found [at this link](#)

Why do I need EOSC?

The Open Science added value for this Test Science Project is that all the digital objects within these new DM analyses will be implemented within the ESCAPE services infrastructure (Data Lake, Software Catalogue, Analysis Platform). We will make use of the ESCAPE Data Infrastructure for Open Science in the European Open Science Cloud to store, distribute and provide data and software access to the broad dark matter scientific community. This is a unique link between DM as a fundamental science question and the Open Science services needed to answer it that benefits the scientific community as a whole. This will serve as a stepping stone to build a virtual research environment within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

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